

Synthesis and electrochemical studies of 4-[(*E*)-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzenylidene)amino]-*N*-(substituted)benzenesulfonamide

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Abstract : Some new 4-[(*E*)-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzenylidene)amino]-*N*-(substituted)benzenesulfonamides were synthesized by condensation between aldehyde with different sulphanamide derivatives. Electrochemical behaviour of 4-[(*E*)-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzenylidene)amino]-*N*-(substituted)benzenesulfonamides have been studied in Britton-Robinson buffers of pH 2.5–12.0 at dropping mercury electrode. All benzenesulfonamides gave one electron wave corresponding to the reduction of -C=N- bond at mercury electrode. On the basis of differential pulse polarography, IR, mass and ¹H NMR spectral studies and product identification, a reduction mechanism has been suggested.

Keywords : 4-[(*E*)-(4-Hydroxy-3-methoxybenzenylidene)amino]-*N*-(substituted)benzenesulfonamides, differential pulse polarography.

Introduction

Imines represent an important class of organic compound, especially in the medicinal and pharmaceutical. Imines are generally known as Schiff bases to honour Professor Hugo Schiff, since their synthesis was first reported by Schiff¹. Structurally, imine is a nitrogen analogue of an aldehyde or ketone in which the carbonyl group (C=O) has been replaced by an imine or azomethine group. The condensation of primary amines with aldehydes and ketones give imines. Imines that contain an aryl group bound to the nitrogen or to the carbon atom are called Schiff bases. Imines derivatives are very important because of their varied structures and biological activities^{2,3}. They are the important compound owing to their wide range of biological activities and industrial application. They have been found to possess the pharmacological activities such as antimicrobial, antipathogenic, antidepressant, antiviral^{4–11}.

The electrochemical behaviour of imines^{12–17} has been studied in both aqueous and non aqueous solutions. Fry and Reed¹⁸ investigated the reduction mechanism of different imines in DMF using polarography, cyclic voltammetry, coulometry and preparative scale electrolysis. Kuder *et al.*¹⁹ studied the series of salicylaldehyde

imines and rationalized the effect of substituents and intramolecular hydrogen bonding. Prasad *et al.*²⁰ observed that *N*-(benzylidene)-2-aminopyrimidine is reduced in a two electron transfer in the pH range 9.8–12.0. Unver *et al.*^{21,22} reported the electrochemical study of 1-[(3-halophenyl)imino]methyl}-2-naphthol and derivatives on graphite electrode, and proposed mechanism for irreversible electrode process. The reduction potential of various imines was stated to be dependent on the size of aromatic groups at either side of the -C=N- group²³, the types of substituents attached to the aromatic ring^{24–26} and intermolecular hydrogen bonds^{27,28}.

Experimental

Synthesis of 4-[(E)-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzenylidene)amino]-N-(substituted)benzenesulfonamides :

For the synthesis of 4-[(*E*)-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzenylidene)amino]-*N*-(substituted)benzenesulfonamides. A solution of substituted aromatic aldehydes (0.01 *M* in 5 mL ethanol) contain allyl and allyloxy group i.e. 4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzaldehyde, 5-methoxy-2-nitro-(prop-2-en-1-yloxy)benzaldehyde, 4-hydroxy-3-methoxy-5-(prop-2-en-1-yl)benzaldehyde was taken in a flask and sulphonamide derivatives (0.01 *M*; 5 mL ethanol) i.e.

sulphanilimide, sulphamethoxazole, sulphathiazole and sulphadimidine was slowly added with continuous stirring. The contents of the flask were refluxed for four hours and left over night in ice bath. The imine separated out, collected and further purified by recrystallization from ethanol. The colour of the synthesized products was in the shades of pale yellow to yellow with a yield percentage of 68%, 75%, 98%, 70% °C. The IR spectra of 4-[(*E*)-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl)methylidene]amino)-benzenesulfonamide is (KBr, cm^{-1}) 3400 (O-H), 1670 (CH=N), 1139 (S=O); ^1H NMR ($\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ ppm : 3.75 (3H, s, CH), 3.0 (1H, s, OH), 5.2–7.2 (3H, m, Ar-CH), 8.4 (1H, s, CH=N), 7.6 (2H, t, CH), 7.9 (2H, t, CH), 2.2 (2H, s, SO_2NH_2). The other compounds of the series were synthesized in the similar manner.

Reagent and solution :

All chemicals were obtained from Aldrich Chemical Co., Germany. Double distilled water was obtained from Millipore (Milford, MA) Milli-Q plus system. 1.0 M KCl in double distilled water was prepared. Britton-Robinson buffers in the pH range 2.5 to 10.5 were prepared using boric acid, orthophosphoric acid, acetic acid and NaOH. All chemicals used were analytical reagents and were employed without further purification. Solutions for recording voltammograms were prepared by adding buffers of varying pH to the stock solution and 1 mL KCl, (1.0 M) as supporting electrolyte. The stock solution of synthesized 4-[(*E*)-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-amino]-*N*-(substituted)benzenesulfonamides (5×10^{-4}) were prepared in DMF respectively.

Fig. 1. A typical polarogram of 4-[(*E*)-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)amino]-*N*-(substituted)benzenesulfonamide derivatives.

Equipments :

The IR spectra were recorded using KBr on Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR spectra in DMSO on a BRUKER FT-NMR instrument using TMS as internal standard and chemical shift values were expressed in ppm. The differential pulse polarographic (DPP) measurements were carried out using ELICO CL362 Polarographic Analyzer (India). The drop time of 1 s was electronically controlled using a 663 VA stand. A three-electrode system composing of a working dropping mercury electrode (DME), saturated calomel electrode (SCE) as reference electrode and platinum wire as an auxiliary electrode were used. Triple distilled mercury was used for this purpose.

The pH-metric measurements were made on a Digital pH Meter MK VI provided with a glass electrode and a saturated calomel electrode as reference. It was standardized with buffers of known pH and used for ascertaining pH of the prepared buffers.

Results and discussion

The voltammetric behavior of the synthesized compounds was examined in the pH range 2.0–12.0 employing DPP and CV techniques. A typical differential pulse polarogram has been depicted in Fig. 1. All the compounds gave one well defined, one electron reduction peak process was observed due to the presence of imine

(-C=N-) groups. The reduction wave observed due to imine linkage appears to be influenced by the catalytic hydrogen evolution. After attaining the neutral pH, the peak current decreases in the basic medium, this again confirms the participation of protons in the reduction process. The polarographic wave is pH dependent. The peak potential shifted towards more negative potential with the rise in pH for all the compounds indicating the participation of protons in electrode process (Fig. 2). Increase in pulse amplitude correspondingly enhances the peak current values, further suggesting the diffusion controlled nature of the electrode process (Fig. 3). It was observed that peak potential shifted towards more negative poten-

Fig. 2. Plot of E_p vs pH of 4-[(*E*)-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxy-benzylidene)amino)]-*N*-(substituted)benzenesulfonamide compound.

Table 1. Differential pulse polarographic (DPP) characteristics of 4-[(*E*)-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)amino)]-*N*-(substituted)benzenesulfonamide

Sr. no.	R	$-E_p$ (V)	i_d (μ A)	αn_a	I	$\partial E_{1/2}/\partial \text{pH}$ (V/pH)	$D_0^{1/2}$ ($\text{cm}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$)	$K_{f,h}^0$ (cm s^{-1})
1.	-H	1.80	4.61	0.3676	0.7329	0.0813	3×10^{-2}	4.0×10^{-6}
2.		1.41	12.65	0.09	0.6426	0.0667	2.6×10^{-2}	1.86×10^{-4}
3.		1.26	6.91	0.2788	0.6011	0.0716	2.5×10^{-2}	2.5×10^{-5}
4.		1.36	4.32	0.209	0.5656	0.0704	2.3×10^{-2}	5.6×10^{-4}

tial with increase in the concentration (Fig. 4). This behaviour pointed towards the irreversible nature of the wave, which was confirmed by log plots. The value of

Fig. 3. Plot of i_d vs pulse amplitude of 4-[(*E*)-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)amino]-*N*-(substituted)benzenesulfonamide compound.

Fig. 4. Plot of i_d vs concentration of 4-[(*E*)-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)amino]-*N*-(substituted)benzenesulfonamide compound.

Fig. 5. Plots of $-E_d$ vs $[\log (i/i_d - i) - 0.546 \log t]$ of 4-[(*E*)-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)amino]-*N*-(substituted)benzenesulfonamide compound.

slope of the plots of $-E_{de}$ vs $[\log (i/i_d - i) - 0.546 \log t]$ exceeded appreciably $0.059/n$ mV, confirming the irreversible nature of the electrode process (Fig. 5).

The related data of differential pulse polarographic (DPP) characteristics of 4-[(*E*)-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)amino]-*N*-(substituted)benzenesulfonamide are in Table 1.

Reaction mechanism :

On the basis of differential pulse polarography and

spectral studies following mechanism has been postulated for the reduction of 4-[(*E*)-(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)amino]]-*N*-(substituted)benzenesulfonamide derivatives series. The general sequence for addition of protons and electrons viz. e^- , H^+ , e^- and H^+ , e^- are given in Scheme 1.

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